

ENHANCED MECHANICAL AND ELECTRICAL PROPERTIES OF IN-SITU CROSS-LINKED BUCKYPAPER

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1 Introduction

Since their discovery in 1991 [1], carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have attracted attentions of a wide range of research fields, partly due to their exceptional mechanical and electrical properties. CNTs are stiff and strong, exhibiting Young's modulus in a range of 1-2 TPa and fracture stress as high as 50 GPa [2, 3], yielding a density-normalized strength ~50 times larger than that of steel wires. The graphene-like wall structure also endows CNTs with high electrical conductivities that associate with the in-plane properties of graphene [4]. Among the endeavors to explore applications of CNTs in devices, one of the most successful is developing the CNT films. Free-standing CNT films, commonly referred to as buckypaper [5], is a macroscopic planar structure comprising of entangled or assembled CNTs [6, 7]. In a format unlike the individual CNTs, this porous fibrous material has been developed with the aim to exploit and homogenize the excellent properties of CNTs, *e.g.*, the superior mechanical and electrical properties, from a nano-scale to a macro-scale, for various engineering applications.

Buckypaper can be infused with resin and manufactured into composites, or easily be incorporated into conventional fiber-reinforced composites [8]. Unlike the composites with CNTs dispersed in the matrix, buckypaper based composites can achieve a much higher concentration of CNTs and high conductive tube networks to maximize the electrical conductivity and mechanical property, as well as the microwave absorption. This provides a new technical approach toward realizing microwave absorption/structural multifunctional composites, which can be potentially applied in the aerospace industry. To achieve this goal, buckypaper with better mechanical, electrical and microwave absorption properties are needed.

Among the techniques for fabricating buckypaper, the vacuum filtration is one of the most widely used wet approaches and closest to structural applications as it can be conveniently scaled and are compatible of a wide variety of substrates [9]. Compared with other wet approaches, it is even more attractive for it can (1) cost-effectively adjust the film homogeneity by the filtration process itself [6], (2) precisely control the film thickness by the filtration time and CNT solution concentration, (3) be conveniently applied to various or mixed types of CNTs and carbon nano-fibers [10], and most importantly, (4) provide large room for modification of the nano-components. However, to date, this remarkable structure generated from vacuum-filtration still has not taken full advantage of the superior mechanical and electrical properties of CNTs. This has been ascribed by researchers to the lack of effective stress and current transfer mechanisms between CNTs. According to Sastry's theory [11], the mechanical performances of a large class of porous, fibrous materials are largely dominated by the stress transfer abilities of the network joints. A finite element simulation on CNT networks conducted by Berhan *et al.* [12], with special emphasis on the tube joint morphologies, also established that the mechanical properties of the buckypaper were determined by the nature of the joints between individual tubes. However, a conventionally produced buckypaper, inter-tube interactions of which were primarily weak van-der-Waals forces and mechanical entanglements, possessed Young's modulus less than 1 % of the individual CNTs [12]. Researchers also found that the high contact resistance between CNTs limited the realization of high conductivity in the buckypaper and the increase of inter-tube contacts can reduce the contact resistance [13].

In this context, covalent bonded cross-linking of CNTs is a reliable way to improve the mechanical

and electrical properties of the buckypaper, for the inter-tube linker can act as an effective stress and current transfer medium between CNTs [14]. Using an atomic force microscope, a 30-fold increase of the bending modulus of a CNT bundle was observed by Kis *et al.* [15], due to the inter-tube cross-linking generated by the moderate electron-beam irradiation inside a transmission electron microscope. Ventura *et al.* and Cha *et al.* introduced inter-tube cross-linking into the CNT network structures [16, 17], and observed an obvious enhancement of tensile strength, bringing the buckypaper closer to practical applications. However, two critical issues still need to be addressed for fabricating the cross-linked buckypapers with significantly improved mechanical performance, as well as electrical property. First, both the chemical functionalization and beam irradiation damaged the intrinsic structure of the CNT, compromising its key characteristic properties, *e.g.*, high Young's modulus and electrical conductivity along the tube axis. Second, in the buckypaper fabricated by Ventura *et al.* and Cha *et al.* [16, 17], the cross-linking of CNTs was conducted in the CNT solution, and then the cross-linked CNT solution was filtrated to obtain the buckypaper. The CNT aggregation in the solution generated from the cross-linking was a problem and reduced the homogeneity of the produced CNT networks, which was critical to the bulk performances of the buckypaper.

In the present study, commercially available plasma purified and functionalized CNTs were chosen, because plasma functionalization is an effective way to graft chemical groups onto the CNT surfaces without significantly damaging the CNT structures [18]. The CNTs were dispersed in solution, and then cross-linked through a substitution reaction by introducing the inter-tube linker of 1,4-benzoquinone. The linker of 1,4-benzoquinone with a conjugated structure was specially chosen with the aim of increasing the inter-tube electron transfer abilities [19]. Influence of the in-solution cross-linking of CNTs on the tube aggregation degree was evaluated. More importantly, in order to avoid increasing the CNT aggregations in the solution, an in-situ cross-linking technique as schematically shown in Fig. 1 was developed to connect individual CNTs in the buckypaper. In this technique, a pristine buckypaper without obvious CNT aggregations was firstly fabricated by a pressurized filtration

technique, and then the pristine CNTs within the buckypaper were in-situ cross-linked by further filtering a 1,4-benzoquinone aqueous solution through the as-fabricated buckypaper. Mechanical and electrical properties of both in-solution and in-situ cross-linked buckypaper were investigated.

2 Experimental

2.1 In-solution Tube Cross-linking

Multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) with diameters ranging from 13-18 nm and lengths ranging from 1-12 μm , were supplied by Cheap Tubes Inc., USA. The MWCNTs were plasma purified and functionalized, with $-\text{NH}_2$ content of about 7 wt% on the tube surfaces. In a typical process of cross-linking CNTs in the solution, MWCNTs (20 mg, with $\sim 8.75 \times 10^{-5}$ mol $-\text{NH}_2$) was added to a well-stirred solution of 1,4-benzoquinone (5 mg, $\sim 4.63 \times 10^{-5}$ mol, purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, UK) in methanol (100 ml) at room temperature. The solution was stirred for various periods of time, after which the suspension was filtered, washed and vacuum dried at 80 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 12 h.

2.2 Solubility Measurement of the In-solution Cross-linked MWCNTs

Water of pH 1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11 and 13 was prepared by adding HCl or NaOH with a pH meter monitoring the pH values. Then, the in-solution cross-linked MWCNTs (0.5 mg) of different reaction time were added to the water (10 ml) with different pH followed by a sonication bath for 5 min. The low density sonication was used since the strong tip sonication would break the inter-tube cross-linking and even the CNT structures [20]. The MWCNT aqueous solution was left still, and zeta potential of each solution was measured as a function of pH values to quantitatively evaluate the solubility of the MWCNTs. The Malvern Zetasizer NanoZS of Malvern Instruments was used for the measurement of zeta potentials of the solutions.

2.3 Buckypaper Fabrication

Same amount of pristine and in-solution cross-linked MWCNTs (20 mg) were dispersed in water (1000

ml) with the addition of 0.5 wt% Triton X-100 by the process of stirring and sonication bath, respectively. Then, the buckypapers were prepared by filtering the solution through a cellulose acetate (CA) syringe filter (Supatop Syringe Filter, 0.45 μm , 33 mm, Anachem) using a programmable syringe-pump (Aladdin AL-100, World Precision Instruments). After the solution filtration, plenty of water was subsequently filtered through the filter to wash away the residual surfactant. Then the buckypaper was dried and immersed into acetone bathes for several times to ensure complete removal of the CA filter. The obtained free-standing buckypaper was vacuum dried at 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ overnight, before cutting into rectangular strips for the mechanical and electrical tests.

2.4 In-situ Inter-tube Cross-linking

For the in-situ cross-linking, the as-prepared buckypaper was washed and kept in the filter. Then, a 1,4-benzoquinone solution was prepared by dispersing 1,4-benzoquinone (5 mg) in water (1000 ml) with a sonication bath. The in-situ inter-tube cross-linking was conducted by filtering the 1,4-benzoquinone solution through the as-prepared buckypaper for various periods of time. During the filtration, air bubbles were introduced intentionally into the filtration setup (Fig. 2a), as required by the cross-linking chemical reactions. After the filtration, the in-situ cross-linked buckypaper was washed, removed from the filter, and dried.

2.5 FTIR and TGA Characterization

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was employed to investigate the functional groups on the walls of MWCNT before and after inter-tube cross-linking, in air at room temperature, on a Perkin Elmer Spectrum-100 FTIR spectrometer. The degree of functionalization was characterized by thermo gravimetric analysis (TGA). The TGA test was conducted at a ramp rate of 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ in the presence of air.

2.6 Scanning Electron Microscopy

The buckypaper micro-morphologies were investigated using a field emission scanning electron

microscopy (SEM, JEOL JSM-6330F) operated at an accelerating voltage of 10 kV. Pore diameter distributions of the buckypapers cross-linked with two techniques were analyzed following the method described in our previous study [21], using an image analysis program (Image-Pro Plus 6.0).

2.7 Mechanical and Electrical Measurements

Tensile strength measurement of the buckypaper strips (25 mm \times 3 mm) were carried out using an Instron 3343 tensile apparatus with a load cell of 10 N, at a constant loading speed of 0.1 mm/min. For the Poisson's ratio measurement, the buckypaper specimen surfaces were coated with reflective micro-particles for marking positions. Movements of these particles were recorded during constant-rate deformation using a single video camera (SONY XCD-X710). Then an image correlation software (Imetrum Video Gauge) was used to derive the relative displacements of the particles per moved frame and corresponding strains in lateral and tensile directions. Electrical conductivities of the buckypaper strips (10 mm \times 8 mm) were obtained using a Keithley 2410 1100 V source meter and a commercial four probe test plate.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Cross-linking Processes of Buckypaper

The MWCNT buckypaper was prepared by syringe-filtering the MWCNT solution through a syringe filter using a programmable syringe-pump. The pressurized syringe filtration technique was utilized for it is much quicker than the conventional vacuum-filtration technique, and produced buckypaper with denser MWCNT networks, as well as better mechanical and electrical properties. Another advantage of the syringe filtration technique is that it is programmable and flow rate of the filtration can be precisely controlled.

As schematically illustrated in Fig. 2a, the in-situ cross-linking of the buckypaper was conducted by filtrating the 1,4-benzoquinone solution through the as-prepared buckypaper at a speed of ~ 0.2 mL/min. Chemical reaction scheme for the inter-tube cross-linking is shown in Fig. 2b [22]. Though the minimum energies calculated by Dmol³ of Materials

Studio[®] for 2,5-bis(amino)1,4-benzoquinone and 2,6-bis(amino)1,4-benzoquinone were very close, the steric factors arising from the substituent effect predominated in the reactions and led to only 2,5-diamino MWCNT 1,4-benzoquinone [23].

FTIR spectra of the pristine and cross-linked MWCNTs with labeled bonds are shown in Fig. 3a. The presences of asymmetric and symmetric N-H stretching absorptions (peaks at approximately 3300 cm^{-1}) and N-H bending vibrations (peaks at approximately 1600 cm^{-1}) indicated the presence of primary amine groups on the pristine MWCNT walls, agreeing well with the datasheet. Also the presence of the adsorption peaks at approximately 1600 and 3200 cm^{-1} suggested that secondary amine groups on the cross-linked MWCNT walls exist [24]. The adsorption peaks corresponding to C-OH, O-H and C=O bonds also confirmed that the introduction of 1,4-benzoquinone generated cross-links between different MWCNTs. The degree of functionalization was further characterized by the TGA. A typical TGA test result is shown in Fig. 3b. From the TGA curves it can be seen that the structures of the MWCNTs after plasma functionalization are still nearly integrated since the weight loss is quite low (~12 wt% at 1000 °C), much less than that of the amino-functionalized CNTs by the diazotization method [25]. Additionally, an extra weight loss of about 2 % at 800 °C for the cross-linked CNTs can also be observed. By assuming that the extra weight loss was caused by the loss of the linker of 1,4-benzoquinone, the degree of functionalization can be calculated to be that about one tenth of the $-\text{NH}_2$ groups on the tube walls were cross-linked.

Electrical potential on the particle surface, known as the zeta potential, can be used as an indication of the potential stability of a dispersion system. If all the particles in the dispersion have a large negative or positive zeta potential, the considerable electrostatic repulsion within particles will prevent the aggregations of the particles. However, if the particles have low zeta potential values, then the surface charge may not be able to overcome the van-der-Waals forces between particles, resulting in a high degree of aggregations. The general dividing line between stable and unstable dispersions is generally taken at either +30 mV or -30 mV as described in ASTM Standard D 4187-82. Particles with zeta potentials more positive than +30 mV or more negative than -30 mV are normally considered

stable; while particles with zeta potential between -30 mV and +30 mV are considered unstable and will precipitate sooner or later depending on the density of the aggregations of particles [26]. Hence, to quantitatively predict the stability of MWCNTs in the aqueous solution, zeta potentials of the pristine MWCNTs and MWCNTs cross-linked for various periods of time were measured in this study (shown in Fig. 4a). As it can be seen in Fig. 4a, zeta potential of the pristine $-\text{NH}_2$ functionalized MWCNTs fell in <-30 mV or $>+30$ mV over a wide range of pH values of the aqueous solution, indicating that the pristine amino-MWCNTs can form a homogenous and stable dispersion in water. However, after the inter-tube cross-linking process, zeta potential of the MWCNTs aqueous solution tends to fall in between -30 mV and +30 mV, and as the cross-linking reaction time increases, the zeta potential approaches to zero mV, indicating an increasing degree of the MWCNT aggregations. Being filtered, the increased aggregations brought in by the MWCNT cross-linking will have a negative impact on the homogeneity of the obtained buckypaper. Typical SEM images of the buckypaper fabricated by the two techniques of in-solution and in-situ cross-linking are shown in Fig. 4b and c. Obvious tube aggregations can be observed in the in-solution cross-linked buckypaper, while for the in-situ cross-linked buckypaper, the aggregations are few. A more quantitative analysis of microstructures of the buckypaper was conducted by examining the SEM images with an image analysis program [21], and the obtained apparent pore size distribution histograms are presented in Fig. 4d. All the histograms were fitted with a lognormal probability density function [27]. From the fitted lognormal distribution curves, it can be clearly observed that the in-situ cross-linked buckypaper has a much narrow distribution of pore sizes, indicating rather more homogeneous microstructures than the in-solution cross-linked buckypaper.

Another problem of the in-solution cross-linking technique lay in that the cross-linking of MWCNTs in the solution occurred mainly inside the tube bundles or aggregations, where the tubes were packed closely enough for the inter-tube bridging. This type of cross-linking contributed little to the mechanical performances of the bulk buckypaper. While for the in-situ cross-linking technique, the tubes were randomly distributed, and the abundant

tube junction joints were perfect candidate cross-linking locations. Stress transfer abilities at these locations directly affected the mechanical performances of the bulk tube networks [11].

3.2 Tensile Property and Electrical Conductivity of the Buckypaper

Tensile strength, modulus and Poisson's ratio of the buckypaper were tested and the results are shown in Fig. 5. It was observed that the buckypaper cross-linked in-solution was more brittle than the pristine one (Fig. 5a). The reduced ultimate-strain of the buckypaper cross-linked in solution was presumably due to the inhomogeneous tube networks resulted from the high degree of tube aggregations. But the cross-linking within MWCNT bundles/aggregations still increased the overall inter-tube stress transfer abilities, hence, resulted in the slightly higher tensile strength. Compared with the tensile strength and the ultimate strain of the buckypaper cross-linked in solution, the properties of the in-situ cross-linked buckypaper were increased significantly, indicating that the in-situ cross-linking process was much more effective in improving mechanical properties of the bulk buckypaper owing to the fact that the cross-linked MWCNT joints randomly distributed over the whole buckypaper effectively increased the inter-tube stress transfer abilities. Tensile strength of the buckypaper cross-linked for various periods of time is shown in Fig. 5b. As the reaction time increasing, the degree of inter-tube cross-linking increased. Hence, the tensile strength of the in-situ cross-linked buckypaper increased. After reacting for about 16 h, $-NH_2$ groups on the MWCNT surfaces have been nearly depleted, and the tensile strength of the buckypaper tends to reach a plateau with high value. When it came to the in-solution cross-linked buckypaper, the tensile strength of the buckypaper only increased to a limited extent, because the cross-linking mainly occurred inner tube bundles/aggregations.

In-plane Poisson's ratio of the randomly oriented buckypaper mainly depended on its micro-structures. It can be tuned to either positive or negative values by changing the mixing ratio of single-walled or multi-walled CNTs [28]. The results in this study showed that the Poisson's ratio of the buckypaper can also be tuned by the inter-tube cross-linking of CNTs as shown in Fig. 6a. For the in-solution cross-

linked buckypaper, the inner bundle/ aggregation cross-links exerted little influence on the bulk structures, exhibiting nearly constant Poisson's ratios for different reaction time. In contrast, the Poisson's ratios of the in-situ cross-linked buckypaper changed from positive to negative as the reaction time increased. A simple model (as shown in Fig 6b) was developed to predict the observed negative and positive in-plane Poisson's ratios of the buckypaper before and after in-situ cross-linking process. With the solvents volatilizing, CNT yarns tend to shrink due to the capillary forces, which can be described according to the Young-Laplace equation [29]. The tube yarn shrinkage leads to dumbbell-like tube bundles, with looser ends and a tighter middle, as schematically shown in Fig 6b. In a pristine buckypaper, when it is stretched, tubes overlap on a tube bundle will slide against the bundle with weak inter-tube van-der-Waals forces, and the bundle is stretched to a tight yarn with a positive Poisson's ratio (Fig 6b). However, in an in-situ cross-linked buckypaper, joints between the tubes overlapped and the bundles are cross-linked (Fig 6b). And the tube network is similar to the re-entrant honeycomb with negative Poisson's ratios as shown in Fig 6b [30]. When it is stretched, the middle segment expands, and as a result, the Poisson's ratios of the in-situ cross-linked buckypaper change from positive to negative as the degree of cross-linking increases.

Electrical conductivities of the pristine buckypaper and buckypapers cross-linked by the two different techniques at room temperature are shown in Fig 7. Electrical conductivity of the buckypaper is much smaller than that of the individual CNT, for in the CNT networks the electrical conductivity is limited by the inter-tube contact resistance [31]. In the in-situ cross-linked buckypaper, the conductivity increased for that the cross-linking led to forming a huge amount of inter-tube contact points. After the cross-linking process, the inter-tube linker of 1,4-benzoquinone with a conjugated structure, together with the graphene-like CNT wall structures, formed a large conjugated system (shown in Fig. 2b), and these cross-linking points within the conjugated system were ideal scattering sites for the electron movements [19]. Hence, the inter-tube contact resistance was reduced, resulting in the dramatically improved bulk conductivity of the buckypaper. While for the in-solution cross-linked buckypaper,

the electrical conductivity decreased. Although the in-solution cross-linking increased the inter-tube contact points within the tube bundles/aggregations, the increased tube aggregations decreased the inter-tube contact points over the whole CNT networks.

4 Conclusions

In this study, a substitution reaction between 1,4-benzoquinone and amino-MWCNTs was introduced for cross-linking the MWCNTs in the buckypaper through an in-solution and an in-situ cross-linking techniques. Zeta potentials of the MWCNTs cross-linked in solution and micro-structure characterization results of the in-solution cross-linked buckypaper indicated that the in-solution cross-linking increased the degree of CNTs aggregations. The CNTs aggregations had a detrimental effective on both mechanical and electrical properties of the bulk buckypaper. While for the in-situ cross-linking technique cross-linked the CNT junction jointed inside the tube networks, increasing the inter-tube stress and current transfer abilities. Hence, the in-situ cross-linking increased both mechanical and electrical properties of the bulk buckypaper much more significantly than the in-solution cross-linking. An interesting phenomenon of Poisson's ratios changing from positive to negative was observed for the in-situ cross-linked buckypaper. The simultaneous enhancement of the overall properties of the in-situ cross-linked buckypaper as compared to the pristine or the in-solution cross-linked buckypaper prescribed by the unique microstructures established this multifunctional material for a broad spectrum of engineering applications.

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Fig.1. Schematic of the in-situ and in-solution techniques for cross-linking the buckypaper.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2 (a) Schematic of the in-situ cross-linking process; (b) reaction scheme for the cross-linking of MWCNTs.

a

Fig. 3 (a) FTIR spectra of pristine and cross-linked MWCNTs with labeled bonds; (b) typical TGA test results for the pristine and cross-linked amino-MWCNTs.

Fig. 4 (a) Zeta potential values of MWCNT dispersions as a function of pH values; SEM images of (b) in-solution cross-linked and (c) in-situ cross-linked buckypaper; (d) apparent pore size distribution histograms of the buckypaper cross-linked for 16 h.

Fig. 5 (a) Representative tensile stress-strain curves of pristine buckypaper, buckypaper in-situ cross-linked for 16 h and in-solution cross-linked for 16 h; (b) tensile strength of buckypaper cross-linked for various time.

Fig. 7 Electrical conductivities of pristine buckypaper and buckypaper cross-linked by the two different techniques.

Fig. 6 (a) Poisson's ratios of the buckypaper cross-linked for various time; (b) a dumbbell-like CNT bundle with CNTs overlapped on the top; a CNT bundle un-cross-linked with the overlapped CNTs being stretched to a tight yarn with a positive Poisson's ratio; a CNT bundle cross-linked with the overlapped CNTs being stretched to expand the middle segments and exhibiting a negative Poisson's ratio; a re-entrant honeycomb model with negative Poisson's ratio for the in-situ cross-linked buckypaper [29].

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